

Mexican dairy farms producing energy and organic fertilizers

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Abstract

In the Comarca Lagunera, Mexico's main dairy-producing region, several farms have implemented covered anaerobic lagoons to convert manure into biogas and organic fertilizers. This study evaluated seven lagoons to assess their operational conditions and potential for improvement. Measurements included pH, organic matter content, methane and hydrogen sulfide concentrations, and temperature profiles. Results revealed that most lagoons operate below the optimal mesophilic temperature range, limiting methane production. Additionally, elevated hydrogen sulfide levels were detected, which can reduce biogas quality and damage metallic equipment. The findings suggest that improving temperature control, manure feeding rates, and gas purification could enhance energy recovery efficiency and fertilizer quality. These adjustments would allow existing systems to fulfill their potential as sustainable technologies for waste management, renewable energy generation, and environmental protection in Mexico's dairy sector.

Keywords

biogas; anaerobic lagoons; dairy farms; renewable energy; organic fertilizers; methane; hydrogen sulfide; Comarca Lagunera; Mexico

In the Comarca Lagunera, the region with the highest dairy and livestock production in Mexico, some farms are using covered anaerobic lagoons that help manage manure more efficiently while simultaneously generating renewable energy and agricultural inputs. This technology converts animal manure from farms into biogas, a clean energy source that can be used to produce electricity and/or heat, while also generating organic fertilizers.

These covered lagoons help make agricultural and livestock operations more sustainable by reducing the pollution caused by manure. They allow dairy farms to transform what was once a problem into a great opportunity to generate electrical and/or thermal energy and to replace chemical fertilizers with organic ones, all while protecting the environment.

A series of measurements were carried out both in the lagoons themselves and in the laboratory to understand the current condition of the covered anaerobic lagoons installed years ago in the Comarca Lagunera. Samples were taken at different points in seven lagoons: the upper part, the middle, and the bottom, where sludge generally accumulates. Figure 1 shows the sump where several samples were collected.

Figure 1. Manure homogenization sump.

These samples were analyzed for important aspects such as pH (which indicates whether the mixture of water and manure is acidic or alkaline), the amount of organic matter that can be decomposed, and the potential biogas production. Other key parameters were also measured, including the methane and hydrogen sulfide content in the biogas, since the quality of the biogas is crucial to determine the amount of energy that can be produced. Figure 2 shows the measurement of these parameters.

Figure 2. Sampling and parameter recollection.

The objective of these measurements was to understand what is happening inside the digester during the process of converting manure into biogas for energy use, as well as to assess the quality of the final residue for use as organic fertilizer. Additionally, the goal was to identify potential adjustments to improve the efficiency of the anaerobic lagoons.

The results showed that, in most cases, the covered lagoons are not operating properly, which helped identify areas for improvement to make the process more efficient.

For example, it was found that the internal temperature of the lagoons was below the level required by the bacteria to produce biogas efficiently. By increasing the temperature, it would be possible to generate more biogas with a higher methane content—the main component of biogas—but this would involve higher operational costs for the farm owners.

Another important finding was the high levels of hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) in the biogas. These high concentrations affect biogas quality and can damage metallic equipment. As a solution, it is recommended to install special filters that help remove this compound from the biogas, improving its quality and extending the service life of the equipment.

Additionally, the study showed that some lagoons are not receiving the required amount of manure. By adjusting the amount of manure fed into the lagoons, it would be possible to increase both biogas production and the volume of organic fertilizer, making the system more efficient.

Although the lagoons were installed quite some time ago, they are not currently operating adequately. However, by implementing the mentioned adjustments, their performance could be greatly improved—allowing the generation of clean energy while promoting good practices that help reduce the environmental impact of Mexico's dairy sector.

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